

Review on method development and validation of pharmaceutical dosage form by using UV visible spectroscopy and HPLC

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Abstract

UV visible Spectroscopy is a form of absorption spectroscopy; Spectroscopy is often used in physical and analytical chemistry for the identification of substance through the spectrum emitted from or absorbed by them. Spectroscopy is also heavily used in astronomy and remote sensing. Most large telescopes have spectrometer, which are used either to measure the chemical composition and physical properties of astronomical objects or to measure the velocities from the Doppler shift of their spectral lines.

High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is an important qualitative and quantitative technique, generally used for the estimation of pharmaceutical and biological sample. It is the safest versatile, dependable and fastest chromatographic technique for the quality control of the drug component.

Keywords: High Performance Liquid Chromatography; Principle; Instrumentation; Method Validation; Method Development; Application; Mobile Phase

1. Introduction

The spectrophotometer also called as workhorse of the modern laboratory. Ultraviolet and visible spectrophotometer are the methods used for identification and measurement of organic and inorganic compounds. In branch of medicine, life science, molecular biology the essential tool is spectrophotometer.

HPLC- High Performance Liquid Chromatography or High-Pressure Liquid Chromatography. HPLC is really the automation of traditional liquid chromatography under conditions which provide for enhanced separation during shorter period of time, utilizing very small particles, small column diameters, and very high fluid pressures.

2. UV visible spectroscopy

2.1. History of UV visible spectroscopy

The spectrophotometer was invented in 1940, by Arnold J. Beckman and his colleagues at National Technologies Laboratories, the company Beckman had started in 1935. They were led by project leader Howard H. Cary. The spectrophotometer was the company's greatest discovery. Once through the sample, the light collected in phototube for measurement.

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2.2. Introduction of UV visible spectroscopy:

UV-Visible spectroscopy is an analytical technique that measures the number of discrete wavelengths of UV or visible light that are absorbed by or transmitted through a sample in comparison to a reference or blank sample. The light plays an important role in this spectroscopy. Light has certain amount of energy which is inversely proportional to its wavelength. Thus, greater wavelength of light carries less energy and longer wavelength carry more energy. Humans are able to see a spectrum of visible light, from approximately 380 nm, which we see as violet, to 780 nm, which we see as red.

2.2.1. Spectroscopy

Spectroscopy is the study of the properties of matter, through its interaction various types of radiation (mainly electromagnetic radiation) of the electromagnetic spectrum. Spectroscopy is an analytical technique.

2.2.2. Spectrometric Techniques

Spectrometric Techniques is analytical methods that are based on atomic and molecular spectroscopy. Spectrometry and spectrometric methods refer to the measurement of the intensity of radiation with a photoelectric transducer or other types of electronic device. Electromagnetic radiation interacts with matter at specific energy levels.

2.2.3. The UV-Visible Spectrometry

It is one of the oldest instrumental techniques of analysis. UV Visible spectrophotometry refers to absorption spectroscopy or reflectance spectroscopy. It is the ideal methods for the determination of micro and semi micro quantities of analytes in a sample. Electromagnetic radiations in the UV and/or visible region with the absorbing species like, atoms, molecules or ions.

It is analytical method that measures the amount of discrete wavelength of UV or visible light. This property will affect by sample composition. This spectroscopy technique relies on the use of light.

Light has certain amount of energy which is inversely proportional to its wavelength. Thus, greater wavelength of light carries less energy and longer wavelength carry more energy. Humans are able to see a spectrum of visible light, from approximately 380 nm.

The electron in different bonding environment in a substance require different specific amount of energy to promote the electron to higher energy state.

2.2.4. Beer's Lambert's Law

When light is incident on homogeneous medium a part of incident light is absorbed, a part is reflected and remaining is allow to transmit.

$$P_o = P_a + P_t + P_r$$

2.2.5. Lambert's Law

A beam of monochromatic light is allowed to pass through a transparent medium the rate of decrease in intensity of light with thickness of medium is directly proportional to intensity of incident light.

$$- \frac{dI}{dt} \propto I$$

2.2.6. Beer's Law

When a beam of monochromatic light is allowed to pass through a transparent medium the intensity of beam of monochromatic light decrease exponentially with concentration absorbance substance arithmetically.

$$A = a.b.c.$$

3. How does UV visible spectrometer work?

There are many variations on the UV-Visible spectrophotometer, to gain a better understanding of how an UV Visible spectrophotometer works, let us consider the main components.

3.1. Instrumentation of UV visible spectrophotometer

It consists of important instrumental component are as follows:

- Radiation Source
- Wavelength selector
- Sample holder
- Detector
- Amplifier
- Recorder

3.2. Radiation source

- It should possess following properties
- It must be sufficient intensity for the transmitted energy to be detected.
- It must be stable.
- It must cover entire wavelength region in which it is used.

Following is some examples of radiation sources:

- Tungsten lamp
- Hydrogen discharge lamp
- Deuterium lamp
- Xenon discharge lamp
- Mercury arc lamp

3.3. wavelength selector

Wavelength selector is used to select desired wavelength of radiations. The essential elements of wavelength selector are entrance slit, monochromator and exist slit.

3.3.1. Monochromator

Monochromator select spectral band nearby to the desired wavelength.

- There are 2 types of monochromators
 - Prism
 - Grating

3.4. Sample holder

It also called as cuvette. The sample cell used to hold liquid solution.

- The sample cell should fulfill 3 requirements:
- Must be uniform of construction.
- Must transmit light of wavelength used.
- Must be inert to the solvent.

3.5. Detectors / Transducer

Detectors are used to detect transmitted light which fall on them. When UV visible beam passes through sample holder.

Detectors have 4 types

- Photovoltaic cell
- Phototube
- Photo multiplier tube
- Silicon photodiode

3.6. Amplifier

It enhanced the intensity of signal transfer by detector.

3.7. Recorder

Used to record the signals

There are 3 types of recorders

- Pen recorder
- Chart recorder
- Now day electronic recorders are used.

4. Method development by UV visible spectroscopy

4.1. Quantitative techniques

Single component and multi component analysis

In single component analysis there is determination of single drug or API.

4.1.1. Methods used for single component analysis are

- Use of absorptivity value
- Calibration curve method
- Single point standardization
- Double point standardization

4.2. Use of absorptivity

This procedure is adopted by official compendia, for stable substances which are practically unaffected by variation of instrumental parameters.

The use of standard A (1%, 1cm) or ϵ values avoids the need to prepare a standard solution of the reference substances in order to determine its absorptivity

$$A = a b c$$

Where,

- A= Absorbance of the solution
- a = Standard Absorptivity value
- b = Path length of sample cell
- c = Concentration of solution

4.3. Calibration curve method

- A calibration curve is plotted using concentration Vs absorbance value of 5 standard solutions.
- In this procedure the absorbances of a number 4-6 of standard solutions of the reference solutions at concentrations encompassing the sample concentration are measured and a calibration graph is constructed.
- Calibration data is essential in concentration and absorbance show linear relationship.

4.4. Single point standardization

The single point procedure involves the measurement of the absorbance of a sample solution and of a standard solution of the reference substance. The standard and sample solutions are prepared in a similar manner; ideally, the concentration of the standard solution should be close to that of the sample solution. The concentration of the substance in the sample is calculated from the proportional relationship that exists between absorbance and concentration.

$$C_2 = C_1 * (A_2 / A_1)$$

Whereas,

- C_1 and C_2 = Concentration of Standard and sample
- A_2 and A_1 = Absorbance of standard and sample

4.5. Double point standardization

Occasionally a linear but non-proportional relationship between concentration and absorbance occurs, which is indicated by a significant positive or negative intercept in a Beer's law plot. A 'two-point bracketing' standardization is therefore required to determine to concentration of the sample solutions. The concentration of one of the standard solutions is greater than that of the sample while the other standard solutions have a lower concentration than the sample. The concentration of the substance in the sample solution is given by the equation

$$C_2 = A_1 - A_2[(A_1 - A_2) (C_2 - C_3) + C_1(A_1 - A_2)]$$

4.6. Multicomponent analysis

It includes determination of two or more drug/API in sample.

- Assay as a single component sample.
- Assay using absorbance corrected of interference.
- Assay after solvent extraction of sample
- Simultaneous equation method.
- Absorbance ratio method/Q method.
- Geometric correction method.
- Orthogonal polynomial method.
- Different spectrophotometry.
- Derivation spectrophotometry.
- Simultaneous equation method

If a sample contains two absorbing drugs (X and Y) each of which absorbs at the lambda max of other, it may be possible to determine both drugs by the technique of simultaneous equations. (Vierodt's method) provided that certain criteria apply.

The information required is

- The Absorptivity of X at lambda 1 and lambda 2, a_{x1} and a_{x2} respectively
- The Absorptivity of Y at lambda 1 and lambda 2, a_{y1} and a_{y2} respectively
- The absorbance's of the diluted sample at lambda 1 and lambda 2, A_1 and A_2 respectively

Let C_x and C_y be the conc. Of X and Y respectively in the diluted sample. Two eq. are constructed based upon the fact that at lambda 1 and lambda 2 the absorbance of the mixture is the sum of the individual absorbances of X and Y.

$$\text{At lambda 1 } A_1 = a_{x1}bc_x + a_{y1}bc_y \dots\dots (1)$$

$$\text{At lambda 2 } A_2 = a_{x2}bc_x + a_{y2}bc_y \dots\dots (2)$$

For measurements in 1cm cells, $b=1$.

Rearrange eq. (2)

$$C_y = A_2 - ax_2cx/ay_2$$

Substituting for C_y in eq. (1) and rearranging gives

$$C_x = A_2 * ay_1 - A_1 * ay_2/ax_2 * ay_1 - (ax_2 * ay_2)$$

$$C_y = A_1 * ax_2 - A_2 * ax_1/ax_2 * ay_1 - (ax_2 * ay_2)$$

4.6.1. Absorbance ratio method

The absorbance ratio method is a modification of the simultaneous procedure. It depends on the property that, for a substance which obeys Beer's Law at all wavelength, the ratio of absorbance at any two wavelengths is a constant value independent of concentration or pathlength. It also called as Q method.

$$C_x = \{(QM - Q_y) / (Q_x - Q_y)\} - (A_1/ax_1)$$

$$C_y = \{(QM - Q_x) / (Q_y - Q_x)\} - (A_1/ay_1)$$

Other Applications-

- Detection of conjugation.
- Detection of geometrical isomer.
- Detection of functional group.
- Detection of impurities.
- Molecular weight determination.
- Dissociation constant determination.
- Determination of chemical kinetics.
- Determination of charge transfer transition.
- Determination of tautomeric equilibrium.

4.7. HPLC

4.7.1. History of HPLC

Liquid chromatography was initially discovered as an analytical technique in the early twentieth century and was first used as a method of separating colored compounds. This is where the name chromatography chroma means color, graphy means writing, was derived. A Russian botanist named Mikhail S. Tswett used a rudimentary form of chromatographic separation to purify mixtures of plant pigments into the pure constituents. He separated the pigments based on their interaction with a stationary phase, which is essential to any chromatographic separation. The stationary phase he used was powdered chalk and alumina, the mobile phase in his separation was the solvent. After the solid stationary phase was packed into a glass column, he poured the mixture of plant pigments and solvent in the top of the column. He then poured additional solvent into the column until the samples were eluted at the bottom of the column. The result of this process most crucial to his investigation was that the plant pigments separated into bands of pure components as they passed through the stationary phase. Modern high performance liquid chromatography or HPLC has its roots in this separation, the first form of liquid chromatography. The chromatographic process has been significantly improved over the last hundred years, yielding greater separation efficiency, versatility and speed.

4.7.2. Introduction of HPLC

The early problem with a liquid chromatography was the slow rate at which analysis take place. This problem was largely overcome by advent of high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). In this system pressure is applied to column, forcing the mobile phase at much higher rate.

Factor affecting separation of liquid chromatography is :

- Plate height
- The sample distribution between the stationary and mobile phase.
- And the selection of stationary and mobile phase.

It has found that smaller the particle size, better will be the resolution. Pressure use normally ranges from 30 to 200 atm, a depending on the column use.

4.8. Principle of HPLC

It is known that the resolving power of chromatographic column increases with column length and number of theoretical rates, although there is the limit to the length of the column due to the problem of peak broadening.

The smaller the particle size of the stationary phases, better the resolution. Unfortunately, smaller the particle size, greater the resistance to eluent flow.

4.9. Theory of HPLC

The particle size of the stationary phase material plays a very vital and crucial role in HPLC. In fact, high efficiency stationary phase materials have been researched and developed exclusively for HPLC having progressively smaller particle size termed as micro particulate column packings.

These silica particles are mostly uniform, porous, with spherical or irregular shape, and having diameter ranging from 3.5 to 10 micrometer. High performance liquid chromatography is a chemistry technique is used to separate compounds of interested from a liquid mixture based on chemical and physical properties.

When HPLC is coupled with a spectrophotometric detector, it can be used quantify analytes to provide detailed information on chemical composition of a sample. HPLC is commonly used in quality control or research laboratories in the chemical, agriculture, biotechnology, pharmaceutical, dietary supplement, and cosmetic industries.

4.9.1. Instrumentation

Solvent reservoir and degassing system

- Pump
- Precolumn
- Sample injection system
- Chromatographic column
- Column packing materials
- Detectors

Figure 1 Solvent reservoir and degassing system

4.10. Solvent reservoir and degassing system

Degassing of these solvents should be done to remove air or oxygen dissolved in them, which if present in mobile phase, can rupture the packing of the column or can produce unwanted peaks in chromatogram.

Degassing of mobile phase can be done by

- By filtration under vacuum- Millipore filters are used for filtration of the mobile phase.
- By distillation of mobile phase – when the required mobile phase is distilled under vacuum, the distillate becomes free of dissolved air or oxygen.
- By ultrasonication - Ultrasonication is the sonication using ultrasound i.e. sound with the frequency greater than the upper limit of human hearing (approx 20 KHz).
- By sparging of an inert gas of low solubility- sparging (gas flushing), which involve bubbling a chemically inert gas of low solubility such as Ar or He through the mobile phase. This can be used to remove oxygen and nitrogen that interfere by forming bubbles in the column.

4.10.1. Pumps

The pumps are used to pass mobile phase through the column at high pressure and at control flow rate.

The pumps are categorized into

- Displacement pumps or syringe pumps
- Reciprocating pumps
- Pneumatic pumps
- Constant displacement pumps or syringe pumps

It consist of a large, syringe like chamber equipped with a plunger that is activated by a screw driver mechanism powered by a stepping motor.

4.10.2. Reciprocating pump

It consists of small chamber in which the solvent is pushed back and forth with the help of a motor driven piston or pressure may be transmitted by a diaphragm which is hydraulically pumped by reciprocating piston.

Pneumatic pumps: In this the mobile phase is contained in a collapsible container housed in a vessel that can be pressurised by a compressed gas.

4.11. Precolumn (Guard column)

Precolumn is broader than analytical column. Precolumn is placed between pump and sample injection system. So that only mobile phase is passed through the precolumn. The precolumn is mainly used to remove the impurities from the solvent and thus prevent contamination of the analytical column.

4.11.1. Sample injection system

- It is used to introduce a fixed volume of the sample solution into the mobile phase.
- The sample injectors are of the following types:
- Syringe injection: - This is the earliest and simplest technique. Hence the sample is injected through a self sealing elastomeric septum and the syringes are designed to withstand pressure upto 1500 psi.
- Stop flow injection: - In this a fitting at the column head is removed and sample is injected directly onto the head of the column packing at atmospheric pressure. Then the fitting is replaced and the system is again pressurised.
- Solvent flowing: - This type of injectors is usually used for injecting sample volumes more than 10 microliter. In the fill position the sample loop is filled at atmospheric pressure. When the valve is actuated the sample in the loop is also actuated.

4.12. Chromatographic column

Usually constructed from smooth bore stainless steel tubing or heavy-walled glass tubing.

The columns are of 2 types

4.12.1. Analytical column

Size: Length: 25 to 100 cm with internal diameter: 2 to 6 mm.

4.12.2. Preparative column

Size: Length: 25 to 100 cm and internal diameters: 6 mm or more.

4.13. Column packing materials

Two basic types of packing have been used in HPLC

Pellicular

4.13.1. Porous Particle

- Pellicular: It consists of small spherical glass or polymer beads with a diameter of 30 to 40 μm uncoated with 1 to 3 μm layer of a porous material such as silica gel, alumina or an ion exchange resin.
- Porous Particle: These particles have diameter ranging from 3 to 10 μm and are composed of silica, alumina or an ion exchange resin.

4.13.2. Detectors

A detector is required to sense the pressure and the amount of sample component in the column effluent. The output of the detector is an electrical signal that is proportional to some property of the mobile phase and/or the solute.

A detector that measures property which is possessed by both mobile phase and solute called as Bulk property detector. E.g. refractive index detector, conductivity detector.

Alternatively, if the property is possessed essentially by the solute e.g. absorption of UV visible light or electrochemical property, the detector is called as Solute property detector. E.g. UV detectors, Fluorescence detector.

4.14. Method development on HPLC

A step involved in method development of HPLC is as follows

- Understanding the Physicochemical properties of drug molecule
- Selection of chromatographic conditions
- Developing the approach of analysis
- Sample preparations
- Method optimization
- Method validations

5. Understanding the Physicochemical properties of drug molecule

Physicochemical properties of a drug molecule play an important role in method development. For Method development one has to study the physical properties like solubility, polarity, pKa and Ph of the drug molecule. Polarity is a physical property of a compound. It helps an analyst, to decide the solvent and composition of the mobile phase. The solubility of molecules can be explained on the basis of the polarity of molecules. Polar, e.g. water, and non-polar, e.g. benzene, solvents donor mix. In general, like dissolves like i.e., materials with similar polarity are soluble in each other. The selection of mobile phase or diluents is based on the solubility of analyte. The analyte must be soluble in diluents and must not react with any of its component. Ph and pKa plays an important role in HPLC method development. The Ph value is defined as the negative of the logarithm to base 10 of the concentration of the hydrogen ion.

$$pH = -\log_{10} [H_3O^+]$$

Selecting a proper Ph for ionisable analytes often leads to symmetrical and sharp peaks in HPLC.

Sharp, symmetrical peaks are necessary in quantitative analysis in order to achieve low detection limits, low relative standard deviations between injections, and reproducible retention times.

5.1. Selection of chromatographic conditions

Selection of column: Selection of the stationary phase/column is the first and the most important step in method development. The development of a rugged and reproducible method is impossible without the availability of a stable, high-performance column. To avoid problems from irreproducible sample retention during method development, it is important that columns be stable and reproducible. A C8 or C18 column made from specially purified, less acidic silica and designed specifically for the separation of basic compounds is generally suitable for all samples and is strongly recommended. Column dimensions, silica substrate properties and bonded stationary phase characteristics are the main ones. The use of silica-based packing is favored in most of the present HPLC columns due to several physical characteristics.

Buffer Selection:

Choice of buffer is governed by the Ph that is desired. The typical Ph range for reversed phase on silica-based packing is Ph 2 to 8. It is important that the buffer has a pKa close to the desired Ph since buffer controls Ph best at their pKa. A rule is to choose a buffer with a pKa value

5.2. General consideration for buffer selection

- Phosphate is more soluble in methanol/water than in acetonitrile/water or THF/water.
- Some salt buffers are hygroscopic and this may lead to changes in the chromatography like increased tailing of basic compounds and possibly selectivity differences.
- Ammonium salts are generally more soluble in organic/water mobile phases.
- Trifluoroacetic acid can degrade with time. It is volatile and absorbs at low UV wavelengths.
- Microbial growth can quickly occur in buffered mobile phases that contain little or no organic modifier at all. The growth accumulates on column inlets and can damage chromatographic performance.
- At Ph greater than 7, phosphate buffer accelerates the dissolution of silica and severely shortens the lifetime of silica-based HPLC columns.
- Ammonium bicarbonate buffers usually are prone to Ph changes and are usually stable for only 24 – 48 hrs. The Ph of this mobile phase tends to become more basic due to the release of carbon dioxide.
- After buffers are prepared, they should be filtered through a 0.2- μ m filter.
- Mobile phases should be degassed.

5.3. Buffer Concentration

Generally, a buffer concentration of 10-50 Mm is adequate for small molecules. Generally, no more than 50% organic should be used with a buffer This will depend on the specific buffer as well as its concentration. Phosphoric acid and its sodium or potassium salts are the most common buffer systems for reversed-phase HPLC. Sulfonate buffers can replace phosphonate buffers when analyzing organophosphate compounds.

5.3.1. Selection of Mobile Phase

The mobile phase effects resolution, selectivity and efficiency. Mobile phase composition (or solvent strength) plays an important role in RP-HPLC separation. Acetonitrile (I), methanol (MeOH) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) are commonly used solvents in RP-HPLC having low UV cut- off of 190, 205 and 212nm respectively. These solvents are miscible with water. Mixture of acetonitrile and water is the best initial choice for the mobile phase during method development.

5.3.2. Validation

“Validation is the act of proving, by GMPs, that any process leads to the expected results.”In 2000,this definition was modified to read as:

“Validation is documented evidence that the process, operated within established parameters, can perform effectively and reproducibly to produce a medicinal product meeting its predetermined specifications and quality attributes.”

5.4. Parameters of method validation

- Accuracy
- Precision

- Linearity
- Detection limit
- Quantitation limit
- Specificity
- Range
- Robustness
- Limit of detection
- Limit of quantitation

5.4.1. Accuracy

Accuracy is defined as the nearness of a measured value to the true or accepted value. Practically accuracy indicates the deviation between the mean value found and the true value. It is determined by applying the method to samples to which known amounts of analyte have been added. These should be analyzed against standard and blank solutions to ensure that no interference exists. The accuracy is then calculated from the test results as a percentage of the analyte recovered by the assay. It may often be expressed as the recovery by the assay of known, added amounts of analyte. The International Convention on Harmonization (ICH) definition of states that “Accuracy of an analytical procedure is the closeness of agreement between the values that are accepted either as conventional true values or an accepted reference value and the value found.

5.4.2. Precision

Precision is defined as the degree of closeness of a series of measurements obtained using multiple samples of the same substance under specified conditions. Precision may be studied as three characteristics – repeatability, intermediate precision, and reproducibility. Repeatability measures precision under the same conditions over a short time duration. This is done using normal operating conditions and the same equipment as usually used for the given analytical method. ICH guidelines prescribe that at least nine determinations should be run over the range specified for the procedure. Values to be reported include standard deviation, coefficient of variation (relative standard deviation), and confidence interval. Intermediate precision refers to variation occurring within the same testing laboratory. It includes study of day-to-day variation, equipment variation, and analyst variation.

5.4.3. Linearity

Linearity is the ability of analytical procedure to obtain a response that is directly proportional to the concentration (amount) of analyte in the sample. If the method is linear, the test results are directly or by well-defined mathematical transformation proportional to concentration of analyte in samples within a given range. Linearity is usually expressed as the confidence limit around the slope of the regression line.

5.4.4. Detection limit

Limit Detection limit (DL) is defined as the “lowest amount of analyte present in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantities under the stated experimental conditions.” DL is generally expressed in terms of analyte concentration in the sample (as parts per million, or percentage). DL may be established visually, or using signal-to-noise ratios or using data from the standard deviation and slope of the calibration curve.

5.4.5. Quantitation limit

Quantitation limit (QL) is defined as the lowest level of an analyte that can be quantitatively measured under the given experimental conditions. This parameter is generally useful to assay analytes present in very low levels – for example, degradation products or impurities. QL may also be defined as the concentration of a related substance in the sample that produces a signal-to-noise ratio of 10:1. QL for a method is influenced by two important factors – the accuracy in sample preparation and sensitivity of the detector used.

5.4.6. Specificity

Specificity is the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present. Typically, these might include impurities, degradants, matrix, etc. Lack of specificity of an individual analytical procedure may be compensated by other supporting analytical procedure(s). This definition has the following implications: Identification: to ensure the identity of an analyte. Purity Tests: to ensure that all the analytical procedures performed allow an accurate statement of the content of impurities of an analyte, i.e. related substances test, heavy

metals, residual solvents content, etc. Assay (content or potency): to provide an exact result which allows an accurate statement on the content or potency of the analyte in a sample.

5.4.7. Range

Range is defined as the interval between lower and upper concentrations of analyte in the sample for an analytical procedure that is demonstrated to possess a suitable level of accuracy, precision, and linearity. Assays must generally have a range of 80 – 120% of nominal concentration. Content uniformity tests must have a range of 70 – 130% of the nominal concentration.

5.4.8. Robustness

The robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage. It is also defined as the capability of an analytical method to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in the method parameters. This characteristic indicates how reliable a given analytical method is during normal usage conditions. Perform experiment by changing conditions slightly such as temperature ($\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$). Buffer pH (± 0.5), ionic strength of buffers, and level of additive to MP. The method must be robust enough to withstand such a slight change and allow routine analysis of the sample.

Limit of detection (LOD)

The smallest amount or concentration of the analyte in the test sample that can be reliably distinguished from zero.

$$LOD = (3.3 \times S.D) \div Slope$$

Limit of quantitation (LOQ)

The lowest concentration of the analyte that can be determined with an acceptable repeatability and trueness.

$$LOQ = (10 \times SD) \div Slope$$

5.5. Applications of HPLC

5.5.1. Preparative HPLC

It refers to the process of isolation and purification of compounds. This differs from analytical HPLC, where the focus is to obtain information about the sample compound. The information that can be obtained includes identification, quantification, and resolution of a compound.

5.5.2. Chemical Separation

it can be accomplished using HPLC by utilising the fact that certain compounds have different migration rates given a particular column and mobile phase. The extent or degree of separation is mostly determined by the choice of stationary phase and mobile phase.

5.5.3. Purification

The process of separating the target compound from other compounds. Each compound should have a characteristic peak under certain sample are chromatographic conditions.

Depending on constituent which have to be separated, the chromatographer may choose the conditions, such as the proper mobile phase, to allow adequate separation in order to collect or extract the desired compound as it elutes from the stationary phase. The migration of the compounds through the column need to differ enough so that the pure desired compound can be collected or extracted without incurring any other undesired compound.

5.5.4. Identification

In order to identify any compound by HPLC a detector must first be selected. Once the detector is selected and is set to optimal detection settings, a separation assay must be developed.

The parameters of this assay should be such that a clean peak of the known sample is observed from the chromatograph. To alter the retention time of a compound, several parameters can be manipulated. choice of column,

5.6. Choice of mobile phase

5.6.1. Choice in flow rate

Identifying a compound by trial-and-error method. A sample of a known compound must be utilised in order to assure identification of the unknown compound. Identification of compounds can be assured by combining two or more detection methods.

5.7. Quantification

The quantification of compounds by HPLC is the process of determining the unknown concentration of a compound in a known solution. The chromatograph of these known concentrations will give a series of peaks that correlate to the concentration of the compound injected.

5.7.1. Medical diagnosis

Because it can be used to separate components from mixtures, HPLC also lends itself to the analysis of nutrients in blood and other medical samples. HPLC can deliver much more precise results when measuring for things like vitamin D deficiency. In this case, rather than measuring vitamin D directly, HPLC can be used to measure the concentration of 5-hydroxyl vitamin D.

5.7.2. Medical research

As well as identifying nutrient levels for a direct diagnosis, HPLC is often used to analyse biological samples from people with existing diagnoses. By identifying specific metabolites in patients with Parkinson's or heart disease, for example, researchers can use them a biomarker to assist with early diagnosis for future patients.

5.7.3. Food production

HPLC can also be used to identify and quantify pesticides along with preservatives and artificial flavorings and colorants.

6. Conclusion

This review describes about RP-HPLC Technique. The method development and validation are continuous and interrelated processes that measure a parameter as intended and establish the performance limits of the measurement. The selection of Column, buffer, detector and wavelength and another conditions composition (organic and pH) play a dramatic role on the separation selectivity The advantages of HPLC technique were high selectivity, sensitivity, economic, less time consuming and low limit of detection. Final optimization can be performed by changing the gradient slope, temperature and flow rate as well as the type and concentration of mobile phase modifiers.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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